

Oxidation kinetics of acetophenone oximes with vanadium(V)

K. Lakshmi Devi*^a and M. Chandraiah Chowdary^b

^aDepartment of Biochemistry, ^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, India

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Oxidation kinetics of acetophenone oxime (APO) and *p*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime (HAPO) by vanadium(V) in aqueous acetic acid medium is reported. The reactions are totally second order, first order with respect to each reactant under second order conditions and negative order with respect to substrate under pseudo-first order conditions. The proposed mechanism involves a two-electron oxidation to the carbocation, which ultimately forms the corresponding keto compound.

Vanadium(V) has been widely used in the oxidation kinetics of different classes of organic compounds¹. In the present communication, the authors report the oxidation of APO and HAPO with vanadium(V) in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Results and Discussion

Under pseudo-first order conditions a negative order with respect to oxime has been observed (Table 1). Using second order conditions the two oxime reactions showed Michaelis-Menten behaviour. The order with respect to oxime was found to be one and zero (Table 2) when the concentration of oxime was 0.5–2 times and more than 2 times of the concentration of V^V respectively, for APO and HAPO reactions. The order with respect to V^V has been found to be one under second order conditions for the two oxime reactions studied (Table 3).

Table 1. Effect of [Oxime] on initial rate under pseudo-first order conditions

[V^V] = 5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ for APO reaction; 0.1 mol dm⁻³ for HAPO reaction, Temp. = 30°, Solvent : 50% aq. acetic acid for APO reaction; 20% aq. acetic acid for HAPO reaction

10 ² [Oxime] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ Initial rate (s ⁻¹)	
	APO	HAPO
2.50	2.64	3.34
5.00	2.20	2.79
7.50	1.34	2.00
10.00	0.91	1.47

At constant μ , the rate of oxidation increased with increasing perchloric acid concentration (Table 4) and the slopes of the plots of log (initial rate) vs log [HClO₄] gave values of 0.6 and 0.5, indicating a fractional order for APO and HAPO reactions respectively. An increase in ionic strength by the addition of sodium perchlorate had a

Table 2. Effect of [Oxime] on initial rate under second order conditions

[V^V] = 5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ for APO reaction; 0.1 mol dm⁻³ for HAPO reaction, Temp. = 30°, Solvent : 50% aq. acetic acid for APO reaction; 20% aq. acetic acid for HAPO reaction

10 ³ [Oxime] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ Initial rate (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	
	APO	HAPO
2.50	1.86	1.25
5.00	3.08	1.97
7.50	3.91	2.48
10.00	4.21	3.20
12.50	4.21	3.58
15.0	4.30	3.68
17.50	4.05	3.71
20.00	4.27	3.80

Table 3. Effect of [V^V] on initial rate under second order conditions in 20% aqueous acetic acid medium at 30°

[APO]₀ = 5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HAPO]₀ = 5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ for APO reaction; 0.1 mol dm⁻³ for HAPO reaction.

10 ³ [V ^V] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ Initial rate (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	
	APO	HAPO
2.50	1.49	0.69
5.00	3.08	1.78
7.50	5.06	2.39
10.00	6.73	3.47
12.50	7.03	4.30
15.00	7.70	5.70
17.50	8.53	6.72
20.00	9.44	8.88

negligible effect on the reaction rate (data not presented).

The stoichiometry was found to be 2 : 1 (V^V : oxime) for the two oxime reactions. The temperature effect was studied in the range 303–318 K and Arrhenius plot of log *k* vs

Table 4. Effect of concentration of HClO₄ on Oxime-V^V reactions at 30° in 20% aqueous acetic acid medium

[V^V] = 5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Oxime] = 5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ Initial rate (s ⁻¹)	
	APO	HAPO
0.05	2.31	-
0.10	2.82	2.79
0.15	3.55	-
0.20	4.15	3.58
0.30	-	4.02
0.40	-	4.00

1/T was linear for the two oxime reactions. The activation parameters were found to be : E_{exp} = 54.66 ± 2, ΔG[#] = 79.59 ± 2, ΔH[#] = 52.14 ± 2, ΔS[#] = -90.55 ± 2, for APO, and E_{exp} = 74.50 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔG[#] = 80.80 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔH[#] = 72.04 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS[#] = -28.80 ± 2 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for HAPO reactions. The constancy of ΔG[#] values indicates that probably the same type of mechanism is operative in the two cases.

It has been suggested that when vanadate salts such as sodium metavanadate, ammonium metavanadate or V₂O₅ are dissolved in aqueous acidic medium, they exist as protonated species² such as V(OH)₃²⁺. The increase in oxidising power of vanadium(V) with increase in [H⁺] is mainly due to the increase in the oxidation potential of V^V species.

The absence of polymerization when acrylamide was added to the reaction mixture under nitrogen atmosphere indicated the absence of free radicals, namely, iminoxy radicals. The negligible effect of added salts on the rate of oxidation indicates that the reaction is either an ion-dipole or dipole-dipole type. As vanadate salts exist as dioxovanadium cation in aqueous medium, the reaction is between vanadium cation and oxime, suggesting an ion-dipole type reaction.

Under second order conditions, the first order dependence on substrate and oxidant suggests the formation of an intermediate complex with one molecule each of oxime and vanadium(V). This is supported by the shift in the absorption to a higher wavelength by about 30 nm in the absorption spectra of the reaction mixture, compared to those of vanadium(V) and oxime solutions. The independence and decrease of initial rate with change in [oxime] can be explained by proposing an intermediate complex between the oxime and vanadium(V). The experimental plots of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[oxime] (not shown) were found to be linear with a positive intercept. This also suggests the formation of an intermediate complex. The formation of the corresponding

ketone was identified by tlc. The formation of V^{IV} was observed from the absorption of reaction mixtures at 760 nm.

Based on the above observation, the reaction is routed by the mechanism shown in Scheme 1. The intermediate complex decomposes to give V^{III} and carbocation. The latter yields the corresponding ketone through the formation of nitrosocarbonyl and with the elimination of nitrous acid. In accordance with the mechanism, the following rate expression is formulated similar to the one proposed by Pillai *et al.*³,

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = k[V(OH)_3^{2+}Oxime] = kK_1K_2[VO_2^+][HClO_4][Oxime] \quad (1)$$

Replacing VO₂⁺ by [V^V]_T, the rate expression takes the form for the disappearance of V^V as

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1K_2[V^V][HClO_4][Oxime]}{1 + K_1[HClO_4] + K_1K_2[HClO_4][Oxime]} \quad (2)$$

The rate expression predicts first order dependence of the rate on [V^V] and [oxime], since 1 is expected to be far greater than the remaining factors in the denominator in accordance with the experimental results.

The decrease in rate with increase in [Oxime] has to be explained. It is postulated that it may be due to the formation of some inert complexes such as 1 : 2 complexes be-

X = H, OH,

Scheme 1

tween vanadium(v) and oxime, similar to the explanation given by Reddy *et al.*⁴. The formation of a 1 : 2 complex takes place when the [Oxime] is just one-and-half times the [oxidant], which causes levelling of the rate. Further increase in [Oxime] increases 1 : 2 complex formation, which causes decrease of the rate. The rate expression is modified to include this equilibrium step,

$$-\frac{d[V^V]}{dt} = \frac{kK_1K_2[V^V][HClO_4][Oxime]}{1 + K_1[HClO_4] + K_1K_2[HClO_4][Oxime] + K_1K_2K_3[HClO_4][Oxime]^2} \quad (3)$$

where K_3 is the equilibrium constant of the 1 : 2 complex. From this rate expression, the fractional order dependence of the rate on $HClO_4$ may be understood. It predicts zero order if 1 becomes negligibly small compared to the sum of the other factors in the denominator and first order when the sum of the factors become negligible in comparison to 1.

The calculated k values ($1.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for APO reaction and $1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for HAPO reaction) indicate that the rate of decomposition of the intermediate complex is slightly less in the case of HAPO. This is due to the decrease in the stability of the carbocation, formed by the decomposition of the intermediate complex (in the case of the HAPO reaction) compared to that in the APO reaction. The contributing factor may be the destabilizing effect of the OH group when it is complexed with vanadium(v).

One would expect a higher rate of complex formation in the HAPO reaction compared to the APO reaction, because of the +M effect of the OH group, which increases the electron density on the nitrogen atom of the oxime. But the experimental K_2 values ($2.3 \times 10^4/K_1$ for APO and $1.0 \times 10^3/K_1$ for HAPO reaction) indicates the low rate of complex formation in the case of HAPO reaction. This may be due to some interaction or coordination between OH group and vanadium species in solution thereby decreasing electron density on the nitrogen atom of the oxime for complex formation.

Experimental

APO was prepared by employing the standard procedure⁵. HAPO (Bioorganics) was recrystallized before use. Sodium metavanadate, ferrous ammonium sulphate and all other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostat at 30° in aqueous acetic acid medium. An aliquot (5 ml) of the reaction mixture was withdrawn at different intervals of time and the reaction was quenched by pouring it into a known excess of standard Fe^{II} solution. The unused Fe^{II} was titrated against standard sodium metavanadate solution using sodium diphenylamine sulphonate as an indicator. Absorption measurements were carried out spectrophotometrically.

Since the plot of $\log [V^V]$ vs t was not linear, the initial slopes were taken for the determination of the order of the reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the initial rates were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. Since the rate of reaction was found to be independent of the [Substrate] under pseudo-first order conditions, the kinetics of the reactions were carried out keeping the [oxidant] at a constant low value and varying the [substrate] from a lower to a sufficiently higher value (0.0025 – 0.02 mol dm^{-3} in one series and vice versa in another series of studies by adjusting the mineral acid concentration for the measurable rate of the reaction).

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